

DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE YEARS AFTER INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: General information about the development of the pre-school education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the years after independence is given.

Key words: Education, child's personality, preschool education, reform, child's personality, socialization, pedagogy, education, road map, adaptation, development.

In the conditions of changes in the field of education, on the one hand, significant changes in all its areas, on the other hand, scientific and technical progress, changes in the nature and content of education, the development of an important and optimal strategy for the development of the field and a new approach and it is natural that it requires solutions. In this regard, there is a need to analyze researches and predictions in the development of social views in society, relevant scientific researches, such analyzes can be carried out only on the basis of scientific-critical and creative approaches, relying on deep knowledge and free thoughts.

In the age of fast and information, everyday life, forms of interaction between people in society, everyone, especially pedagogues, need to make children understand that it is necessary not only to educate children, but also, first of all, to achieve high results and engage in social interaction, and to reveal their individual abilities. It is required to focus. Today, it is an urgent problem to provide the need for people who can actively and constructively solve the contradictions in various fields that exist in the society, have a creative approach, and the ability to take initiative.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev states that "Modern preschool education plays an important role in raising a healthy and mature generation."

Decision of the President of the Republic No. PQ-3305 of September 30, 2017 "On Organization of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and No. PQ-2707 of December 29, 2016 "2017 In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 929 dated November 21, 2017 "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2021" "Regulation of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan quality preparation of children for education, strengthening the material and technical base of preschool educational organizations, expanding the state and non-governmental network of preschool educational organizations, thereby increasing the coverage of children in preschool education, and making it possible to apply advanced foreign experiences to the field. The educational process in preschool educational organizations is planned based on the State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age and the "First Step" state program.

Currently, special attention is paid to the preparation of children for quality school education in preschool education organizations under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Including:

1. Implementation of the "First Step" program in the educational process, the role of methodical support and methodical support in the full development of the program was determined. 2. On the basis of the "First Step" program, special attention was paid to the place of the educator in the organization of centers and general group work in all age groups.

The working curriculum of the educational organization was established by the pedagogues of the organization with the involvement of parents and approved in accordance with the current legislation. In pre-school educational organizations, children work in 5 centers based on the "First Step" state curriculum. These are:

1. Language and speech center. (Speech training, nature, environment and fiction activities)

2. Construction, design and mathematics center. (Building and math activities)

3. Art Center (Painting, appliqué, clay modeling, crafting and origami)

4. Story-role games and dramatized center. (Games with rules that are appropriate for the age of the group)

5. Science and Nature Center. (Activities to introduce nature and the surrounding world)

If we focus on the analysis of the activities in the centers, in the language and speech center, children will have the opportunity to express their opinions among their friends, create stories based on the topic, ask questions, and organize conversations for children. In the center, the child can also create stories on the topic of his choice.

Sensory education and creativity develop in children in the center of construction, construction and mathematics. By completing a task, the child will have the opportunity to do both construction and mathematics. If you listen to children during the game, you will hear sentences like "I need green color", "The house I made has two floors", "Yours is small and mine is big", "I can fit 10 people in my car". Therefore, the first mathematical concepts such as addition, subtraction, comparison, and magnitude expand in children's communication.

There is an opportunity to raise the mood of children in the art center. Children's creative abilities are supported. Not everyone has the same talent for painting, sculpture, and other types of art. Therefore, only talented children participate in it. If the center is fully equipped with the necessary equipment, if the technologies of making and drawing are taught in the morning and evening hours, the work of the center will develop. Such conditions are not always created for the child in the family. Working in the center develops the child's fine motor skills. The development of fine motor skills leads to the development of the child's speech.

Story-role games and a dramatized center are a very comfortable environment for children to show their talents and skills. This center can also be called the center that forms the "I" of the child. All the equipment in the center is the equipment found in children's life, and during the game, the child learns to use them, and has the opportunity to get acquainted with professions. The game reflects the mutual relations of family members and provides an opportunity to receive moral education (and for the educator to study the family environment).

Experiments conducted at the experimental testing ground at the Science and Nature Center arouse interest in children and encourage them to make new inventions. This center is

also the center of the greatest opportunity for children to learn about nature and its phenomena. If the activity of the center is organized correctly, children will learn 90% of the knowledge about nature. The center arouses interest not only in children but also in pedagogues. The information about where the things used in our life come from, what is obtained from them, children sprinkled seeds in pots with their own hands, put water in them and the seeds germinated.

The activity of the above-mentioned centers serves as a developing environment for preparing children for school education, and we considered it permissible to attach a map of school preparation for 6-7-year-old children. After all, the development map of a child of this age determines the success and efficiency of the educational process. For example, in a child,

1. Formation of physical development and healthy lifestyle
2. Socio-emotional development
3. Speech, communication, reading and writing skills
4. Learning (development through understanding)

5. Creative development is the main criteria that prepares him for the school environment.

After the end of the academic year, based on the monitoring of the preparatory group for the school, the comparison of the work done with the expected results is carried out, and through this, priority tasks of the MTT for the next academic year are determined.

In conclusion, it should be noted that working in children's development centers prepares them for school education, so that they grow up mentally and physically mature in all respects, and become loyal to national values and traditions. , increases their interest in the profession.

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